

Beyond Translation: translation as gateway rather than endpoint

White Paper for the National Endowment for the Humanities

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Website: <https://beyond-translation.perseus.org/>

Code: <https://github.com/scaife-viewer/beyond-translation-site>

Overview of features (with animated gifs):

<https://pdldatajournal.pubpub.org/new-features-in-beyond-translation>

Our goal in the Beyond Translation Project¹ is to challenge audiences to view translations as gateways into the original language of the sources which they seek to represent. The potential audience involves anyone who is intrigued by something in an unfamiliar language – lyrics to a song, the words in a movie, social media posts – and who wants to begin exploring what translation cannot express. Open data needed to support such reading had existed for years but was primarily accessible in different platforms, each dedicated to helping others create a subset of annotation classes (and usually just one). While participants in Beyond Translation produced substantial data of their own, they typically used these existing tools. Beyond Translation now allows readers to work with annotations of different types and from different projects within an integrated reading environment. Beyond Translation can now manage the various categories of information that we set out to cover.

With funding from the NEH Humanities Collections and Reference Resources (PW-290565-23), the Tufts Data Intensive Studies Center and Tufts Arts and Sciences, next steps involve refinement of the reading environment and the addition of content at scale. The services available in Beyond Translation will be folded into the Scaife Viewer. The new combined platform will become Perseus 5 and will replace the current production of the Perseus Digital Library (with a planned transition of fall 2024).

2. Project Origins and Goals

A rich collection of tools have appeared that make it possible to create openly licensed annotations of various kinds. These annotations provide the raw materials with which we can

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make primary sources in unfamiliar languages accessible. [Arborator](#), [INCEpTION](#), [Perseids](#) and [Prodigy](#) support some combination of treebanking and named entity classification and linking. Most of those who link place names in Greek and Latin sources to authority lists (named entity linking) use [Recogito](#), which provides immediate access to the Pleiades Gazetteer, efficient semi-automated annotation, and visualization. Entirely separate systems such as [Ugarit](#) allow editors to align words and phrases in a source text with their corresponding words and phrases in the translation. In one case, a single researcher, David Chamberlain, working without any funding, developed [Hypotactic](#), an entire framework to show metrical analyses for 250,000 lines of Greek and Latin poetry. The [Homer Multitext Project](#) published high resolution images of, and a diplomatic edition of, the Venetus A manuscript, which contains not only the text of the *Iliad* but also six accompanying categories of scholarly annotation. The [Digital Latin Library](#) has begun to publish born-digital critical editions that offer reconstructions of Latin works based upon evidence from multiple witnesses and scholarly conjecture. The [International Image Interoperability Framework](#) makes it possible for a single application to call up, via a single API, details of images from museums, art galleries, libraries, archives and other institutions from around the world.

Each of the systems described above concentrates on one or more related types of annotation. No environment yet existed, however, to combine the various annotations into a single reading environment. At Perseus, we had viewed two classes of annotation as foundational. First, word and phrase level alignments show readers which words correspond to which in the source text and translation. Once readers saw a relevant word in the source text, a layer of rich linguistic annotations would make it possible for readers then to see how each word functioned in the original language. The parallel text alignments and the linguistic annotations were intended to reinforce each other but we at Perseus were not able to integrate these two classes of annotation into a single reading environment. Our collaborators at the [Alpheios Project](#) (who funded the first major work on the Perseus Greek treebank) built reading tools that provided an initial model of such a reading environment as early as 2009. Their efforts laid the foundation (and indeed inspired) our work on Beyond Translation.

The study of Greco-Roman antiquity provides a useful starting point to explore this larger problem.

First, students of Ancient Greek and Latin spend much of their effort examining linguistic structure, value systems and general cultural assumptions that cannot be properly translated into English – one could argue that philology begins where translation fails. Much work on Greco-Roman culture assumes that audiences can critically assess the original sources in a way that is not possible with translation.

Second, reliance upon translation has emerged as a challenge and a necessity in departments of Classics. When, in 2021, Princeton made headlines by allowing its students to major in Classics without requiring study of either language,² they were following many other

² E.g., Kokkinidis 2021, Treadway 2021, and Wood 2021. And for some further reflection on the role of reading Greek and Latin, see Nicholson 2023.

departments in conceding that students simply do not have the time to be expected to master either Greek or Latin as undergraduates. Beyond Translation aims to draw those students directly into the language, allowing them to learn as much, or as little, as they need to engage directly with the ancient source.

Third, Greco-Roman culture is an international field. Advanced students of the field have traditionally been expected to work with research publications in languages such as English, French, German, Italian, Spanish and even Latin (a language in which editors still often introduce their editions). While publications in modern European languages, translation may be more adequate than when applied to ancient primary sources, readers should have the ability to inspect a reference work or research publication in the original text.

Fourth, specialists in Greek and Latin often also need to do comparative work with languages that they will probably not be able to master. Very few specialists in Greek or Latin can work with Syriac or Coptic, each of which contains key sources about Eastern Mediterranean culture. Classical Arabic translations of, and commentaries on, Greek scientific and philosophical works have been digitized and published under an open license but only a tiny number of specialists in Greek or Latin can work with these sources.

Fifth, Greek and Latin sources do not enjoy the same prominence as song lyrics or movie screen plays or fiction but they are objects of persistent interest that have been studied and commented on for thousands of years and, we hope, many years to come in the future. Work contributed today has an excellent chance of being relevant and useful long into the future. The idea of participating in a conversation that extends over generations challenges us to think about longer term preservation.

Sixth, many (and perhaps most) of those researchers who work with Greek and Latin sources are in fields such as World or Comparative Literature, Political Science, Philosophy, and Religion. Work done on Homer, for example, has the potential to reach a very wide audience.

Seventh, a vigorous and growing ecosystem of open data projects has emerged in the US and beyond, some funded by a variety of different agencies while others (such as David Chamberlain's [Hypotactic](#)) were the results of purely volunteer effort. We were comfortable in 2019 arguing for work on Greek and Latin because this ecosystem had taken shape when we began work. Our efforts over the four years of work (2019-2023) showed us that this ecosystem is even richer than we had anticipated. We chose to focus particularly on Homeric epic because of its prominence and because of the richness of open data annotations available for it. But even still, there was still more open digital content available for Homeric epic than we could add: e.g., TEI XML transcriptions and accompanying images of literary papyri from Papyri.info, named entity classification and linking to authority lists such as Pleiades and Wikidata in English translations (originally from Perseus) published by [ToposText](#), a growing range of annotations and digitized resources (such as Monro's *Homeric Grammar*) available from the [Dickinson Classical Commentaries](#), and more than 25,000 easily extracted book-and-line citations to Homer in the 27 million word corpus, and TEI XML versions of Dindorf's Homeric Scholia

(produced by the [Open Greek and Latin Project](#) in which Perseus collaborates). That said, we entered enough material so that we have the platform in place to add such new data without adding to the system.

Figure 1: Open data projects upon which Beyond Translation has drawn

But if we did not manage to incorporate all the content that we would have wished (and hope to add going forward), we did manage to integrate the range of annotation types that we wished to cover. Now that we have a working reading environment with the features that we wanted, we naturally need to review and revise our design but we now have the framework into which we can in the future add the content mentioned above.

3. Project Activities, Team and Participants

Our activities fell under three main categories. **First**, developers Jacob Wegner and James Tauber met with PI Crane and other members of the project on a weekly basis, going over progress towards developing the framework for Beyond Translation. **Second**, students

participated, primarily during the summers when they had time for more concentrated work. Students worked both on producing content and on helping to organize content from third party applications. **Third**, a range of activities continued, often associated with teaching, during the academic year. These activities produced some data but were particularly helpful as we decided what content to add and how to structure the reading environment.

As a framework to integrate annotations we used the **Canonical Text Services** (CTS) protocol, which collaborators in the [Homer Multitext Project](#) developed and which allows us to generate explicit, human-readable, machine-actionable URNs that can describe not only a particular chapter/verse style citation but also identify the particular version that we are citing. CTS, thus, provides a standard data model by which to identify a passage not only through a traditional citation scheme (e.g., lines 8-16 of book 1 of the *Iliad*) but also to a particular version (e.g., the *Iliad* as it appears in the Venetus A or the Allen Oxford Classical Text).

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urn:cts:greekLit:tlg0012.tlg001.perseus-grc2:1.8-1.16
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- tlg0012 → Homeric Epics
- tlg001 → the Homeric *Iliad*
- perseus-grc2 → the Allen OCT edition
- 1.8-1.16 → book 1, lines 8-16

CTS provides a simple and transparent format by which to designate any substring in any version of any work within any text group. A text group describes any corpus that has been conventionally treated as a single work, whether by a single author (e.g., the seven surviving plays of Sophocles) or by a group of authors (e.g., the New Testament or the collection of Greek poems by many authors traditionally called the *Greek Anthology*).

Beyond Translation focused on creating a system to aggregate data from multiple systems. Our work addressed three complementary categories of work needed to create an initial reading environment: building the frontend user interface, organizing the backend data and exploring ways to provide credits for new forms of publication.

First, we developed an initial frontend that brings together into a single reading environment classes of annotation that were previously available in separate systems such as those mentioned above. Much work needs to be done to review and revise what we have created but the front end does provide a concrete starting point for future work. One of the biggest challenges before us is simply organizing the range of annotations already available – a generation of open scholarship has produced a gratifyingly rich and thus challenging range of annotation classes. The Beyond Translation reading environment is already crowded, if not cluttered. The need to filter, customize and personalize will only grow as more data is added.

Second, we needed to convert data from different projects into a format that we could use. Even when projects follow the same guidelines and use the same data creation system, they

frequently create data that differs in form and must be normalized before it can be combined. Most open data projects publish their data in the hope of future reuse and many are, in our experience, eager to modify the output formats that they use as they better understand what subsequent users will need. Our hope is that the work that we performed in order to combine data from different sources will help other projects make their open publications even more interoperable.

In 2013, Perseus chose to structure its collections according to the Canonical Text Services (CTS) data model (discussed above). The 2018 [Scaife Viewer](#) builds on the [CapiTainS](#) suite of tools for the serving and processing of CTS-encoded texts. One of the advantages of CapiTainS is that it includes checks to ensure that metadata and internal text markup follow a consistent CTS-compliant scheme. Beyond Translation, however, focuses more upon annotations that are external to the original TEI XML markup – standoff markup, in fact, becomes essential as different classes of annotation comment on every word and even on subsections of words in a text. Jacob Wegner and James Tauber, the scholar developers who designed Scaife and Beyond Translation, developed the ATLAS backend architecture³ to manage an open-ended and expanding range of annotations. ATLAS (Aligned Text and Linguistic Annotation Server) is a collection of open-source, back-end components for ingesting texts, annotations (tagging, treebanks, translation alignments), and resources (lexicons, commentaries) in a variety of formats (including TEI XML, CoNLL-U, CEX, and CSV) and making them available via a GraphQL API. Tokenized texts are served up by CTS URN with annotations stitched together for unified presentation in an online reading environment front-end. ATLAS builds upon the CTS URNs to describe and then unify annotations from multiple sources. Charles Pletcher, then a PhD student in Classics, developed the final version of the IIIF integration and restructured Perseus commentaries to be compatible with Beyond Translation.

Third, and perhaps most importantly, we need to give the most fine-grained and prominent possible credit for any work that we reuse. Those who work with critical editions have experience with detailed credits from print culture, with textual notes attributing readings to one or more manuscript witnesses and suggested corrections not attested in the tradition to their authors. Digital publications can provide very precise levels of credit.

- Two different annotators independently annotated each sentence in the Perseus Treebanks for Homer and Hesiod. A more senior annotator then adjudicated places where the annotators disagreed. Each sentence records all three contributors.
- The New Alexandria Commentary Platform provides individual credits for each traditional annotation.
- Gregory Nagy and his collaborators have spent decades revising older translations, with multiple editors now commonly listed.
- Some of the XML primary sources and reference works in Perseus have been curated for more than thirty years, with elaborate logs for various contributions over time.

³ <https://github.com/scaife-viewer/beyond-translation-site/blob/main/backend/README.md>

We have done our best to provide credits but much work remains to be done. First, we need more conversation within the community as to how to make credits as visible as possible, providing authors and editors with as much recognition as possible but without distracting the actual users. Second and far more challenging, we do not yet know how to manage credits as data circulates among open data projects. When one project imports open data from another, it commonly changes the structure of the digital file and, in so doing, can lose the ability to reproduce the detailed credits that it inherits. We need a method to record scholarly transactions. The Blockchain addresses this general principle. The energy demanded by a traditional blockchain is prohibitive but humanists do not need the same level of security as in core financial assets and so more efficient approaches would surely be available.

4. Project Outcomes

Textual Notes

We are now able to import and display textual variants encoded according to the [TEI XML guidelines for a Critical Apparatus](#). While substantial work has gone into a system that can not only display variants but also show which variants affect syntactic analysis and translation (Rossini 2020, 2021), our goal in this phase of Beyond Translation was to be able to import and display textual variants (the critical apparatus). We wanted to be able to incorporate a full critical edition and then add to it features that go beyond what was possible in print culture. In this we also benefited from investment that a commercial publisher had made in the [Scaife Viewer code base](#), which Perseus developed before beginning its work on Beyond Translation. Brill uses the open source code in the Scaife Viewer to publish its (largely) proprietary scholarly editions at <https://scholarlyeditions.brill.com/> (its [Literary History of Medicine](#) is the one open access project in the Brill Scholarly Editions portfolio). We were able to build on code for textual notes that Brill had added to the Scaife code base.

Two examples are available in the initial release of Beyond Translation. The first example (below) is of interest for at least two reasons.

The image shows a digital edition of Christopher Marlowe's poem "The Passionate Shepherd to His Love". The main text is on the left, with line numbers 1.1 through 6.1. Several words and phrases are highlighted in yellow, indicating textual variants: "mee", "all the pleasures", "Vallies, groves, hills and fieldes", "Woods, or steepie mountaine yeeldes", "And wee will sit upon the Rocks", "theyr", "sing", "And I will thee beds of Roses", "And a thousand fragrant posies", "A cap of flowers, and a kirtle", "A gowne made of the finest wooll", "our pretty", "Fayre lined slippers", "With buckles of the purest gold", "A belt of straw, and Ivie buds", "With Corall clasps and Amber studs", "And if these pleasures may thee move", "Come live with mee, and be my love.", and "The Shepheards Swaines shall daunce and sing,". On the right side, there is a sidebar titled "TEXTUAL NOTES" with a downward arrow. It lists several variants for the highlighted text, each with a source reference: "Come (3)", "live with mee", "And (12)", "all the pleasures", "Vallies, groves, hills and fieldes (7)", "hilles and vallies, dales and fields", "#Passionate Pilgrim, 1599", "valleis, groves, the hills and filds", "#MS corrected, Rawl. Poet. 148, fol. 96, 1600", "hills and valleis, groves and filds", "#MS uncorrected, Rawl. Poet. 148, fol. 96, 1600", "vallies groves and woodds or feildes", "#Thornborough Commonplace Book", "vallies, Groves, or hills, or fields", "#Compleat Angler, Walton, 1653/1655", "#MS Folger Va.169, 1670", "hill or dales woodds or fieldes", "#MS Rodenbach", "grove or valley, hill or field", "#Poems of Sir Walter Raleigh, ed. Sir Egerton Brydges, 1813", and "Woods, or steepie mountaine yeeldes (8)".

1.1 Come live with mee and be my love,
 1.2 And we will all the pleasures prove,
 1.3 That Vallies, groves, hills and fieldes,
 1.4 Woods, or steepie mountaine yeeldes.
 2.1 And wee will sit upon the Rocks,
 2.2 Seeing the Shepheards feede theyr flocks,
 2.3 By shallow Rivers, to whose falls,
 2.4 Melodious byrds sing Madrigalls.
 3.1 And I will thee beds of Roses
 3.2 And a thousand fragrant posies,
 3.3 A cap of flowers, and a kirtle,
 3.4 Imbroydred all with leaves of Mirtle.
 4.1 A gowne made of the finest wooll,
 4.2 Which from our pretty Lambes we pull,
 4.3 Fayre lined slippers for the cold:
 4.4 With buckles of the purest gold.
 5.1 A belt of straw, and Ivie buds,
 5.2 With Corall clasps and Amber studs,
 5.3 And if these pleasures may thee move,
 5.4 Come live with mee, and be my love.
 6.1 The Shepheards Swaines shall daunce and sing,
 6.2 For thy delight each May morning

→

▼ TEXTUAL NOTES

Come (3)
live with mee
And (12)
all the pleasures

Vallies, groves, hills and fieldes (7)
hilles and vallies, dales and fields
 #Passionate Pilgrim, 1599

valleis, groves, the hills and filds
 #MS corrected, Rawl. Poet. 148, fol. 96, 1600

hills and valleis, groves and filds
 #MS uncorrected, Rawl. Poet. 148, fol. 96, 1600

vallies groves and woodds or feildes
 #Thornborough Commonplace Book

vallies, Groves, or hills, or fields
 #Compleat Angler, Walton, 1653/1655
 #MS Folger Va.169, 1670

hill or dales woodds or fieldes
 #MS Rodenbach

grove or valley, hill or field
 #Poems of Sir Walter Raleigh, ed. Sir Egerton
 Brydges, 1813

Woods, or steepie mountaine yeeldes
 (8)

Figure 2: Textual notes for Christopher Marlowe's *Passionate Shepherd*

First, we chose to include this work because it was in English and thus the text would be accessible to a wider audience than examples in Greek, Latin, Arabic or Persian. Second, we chose this because the TEI XML was encoded in the late 1990s and had not been updated. While the XML reflected an earlier version of the TEI Guidelines, the markup for the variants was still useful. While twenty-five years is not a long time in fields such as Greco-Roman studies, we were impressed that the TEI Apparatus Criticus guidelines from a quarter century ago were sufficiently well defined that the data remains useful.

The next example illustrates the possibilities of open scholarship. Cynthia Damon published in the Digital Latin Library (DLL) a major critical edition of the *Bellum Alexandrinum*, a work about the Roman Civil War traditionally ascribed to, but not by, Julius Caesar. Because the DLL not only provides web access to its editions but also the underlying TEI XML textual data under a Creative Commons license, we were able to upload this edition and to provide it with another publication venue.

- 1.1 Bello Alexandrino conflato Caesar Rhodo atque ex Syria Ciliciaque omnem classem arcessit. Creta sagittarios, equites ab rege Nabataeorum Malcho euocat. Tormenta undique conquiri et frumentum mitti auxilia adduci iubet.
- 1.2 Interim munitiones **cotidie operibus** augentur atque omnes oppidi partes quae minus esse firmae uidentur testudinibus ac musculis **aptantur**. Ex aedificiis autem **per foramina in** proxima aedificia arietes immittuntur, quantumque aut ruinis deicitur aut per uim recipitur loci in tantum munitiones proferuntur.
- 1.3 Nam **[ab] incendio** fere tuta est Alexandria quod sine contignatione **ac** materia sunt aedificia **et structuris** ac fornicibus continentur tectaue sunt rudere aut pauimentis.
- 1.4 Caesar maxime studebat ut, quam angustissimam partem oppidi palus a meridie interiecta efficiebat, hanc operibus uincensima agendis ab reliqua parte

→ TOKEN ANNOTATIONS

▼ MORPHOLOGY
Select a word to get morphological analysis (Greek and Latin only).

▼ TEXTUAL NOTES

cotidie operibus (3)
cotidie operibus
#Vatican, BAV Vat. lat. 3324 (s. xi or xii)
#Florence, BML Ashburnham 33 (s. x)
#Paris, BNF lat. 5764 (s. xi).
#Vienna, ÖN 95 (s. xii)

cotidie (cf. BC 3.112.9)
#Florence, BML Plut. lat 68.8 (s. xii or xiii)

nouis cotidie operibus (cf. Tac. Hist. 2.76.4)
#Castiglioni, L. Intorno a Cesare ed ai suoi continuatori (Bellum Civile, Africanum, Alexandrinum). Athenaeum n.s. 11 (1924): 229–40.

aptantur (2)
per foramina (2)
in (2)

Figure 3: Textual notes from a DLL edition of the *Bellum Alexandrinum* published in Beyond Translation

The DLL provides more advanced features for working with the textual notes than the relatively basic services that Beyond Translation currently offers ([compare their version](#), designed by Hugh Cayless, which allows readers to filter out different kinds of textual notes), but the notes and full critical edition are available. Additional contributions to this edition in Beyond Translation will be discussed below: the addition of translation alignments, treebanking and named entity linking (not yet visible but encoded in the data).

Token Level Alignments

In the simplest case, we are able to integrate together multiple categories of annotation that address the space-delimited tokens.

BEOWULF

Lemma Morph. Tag Gloss

1.t1	1.t2	1.t3	1.t4	1.t5
Hwæt!	Wē	Gār-Dena	in	gēardagum,
hwæt	we	Gar-Dene	in	gear-dagas
indeclinable	np	gp	indeclinable	dp
<i>well</i>	<i>we</i>	<i>Spear-Danes</i>	<i>in</i>	<i>days of yore</i>
2.t1	2.t2	2.t3		
þeodcyninga	þrym	gefrūnon,		
þeod-cyning	þrym	gefrignan		
gp	as	p1p		
<i>king of the nation</i>	<i>glory</i>	<i>hear</i>		
3.t1	3.t2	3.t3	3.t4	3.t5
hū	ðā	æþelingas	ellen	fremedon.
hu	se	æþeling	ellen	fremman
indeclinable	npm	np	as	p3p
<i>how</i>	<i>that</i>	<i>prince</i>	<i>deeds of courage</i>	<i>perform</i>
4.t1	4.t2	4.t3	4.t4	4.t5
Oft	Scyld	Scēfing	sceaþena	þrēatum,
oft	Scyld	Scefing	sceaða	þreat
indeclinable	ns	ns	gp	dp
<i>often</i>	<i>Scyld</i>	<i>Scefing</i>	<i>enemy</i>	<i>troop</i>

Figure 4: The opening lines of Beowulf.

In the figure above, each token has a unique ID (line + token number in that line), its inflected form, its standardized dictionary form, a part of speech, and a gloss. We have, for now, kept very brief grammatical tags. In line 2, the tags are gp (“genitive plural”), as (“accusative singular”), and p1p (“1st person plural past tense”). Once readers become accustomed to the basic meanings of these terms, they can see that line 2 would be translated as “We heard the fame of the kings of the nation.”

The columnar format above could be expanded with additional categories of information (e.g., links to information about named entities such as Scyld Scefing in line 4). We could also include a layer showing how a particular translation rendered (or chose to omit) any given word in the Old English source. We could add syntactic information, explicitly stating that *þrym* in line 2 was not just accusative singular but also the object of *gefrūnon*. The simple format presented above

cannot represent many of the annotation classes listed below but it provides a general, base representation that we complement with other methods.

Sentence and word level translation alignments

We have been able to integrate word and phrase level alignments between source texts and translation. In addition, we have also been able to import data from a particular application ([the Ugarit Alignment Editor](#)), from spreadsheets (e.g., the [Persian translation of Iliad book 1](#)), and from an inline annotation scheme that we developed as part of our work (e.g., [the English translation of Odyssey book 5](#)).

Word and phrase level alignments provide a first step beyond translation and into source texts. Having a coherent translation provides the scaffolding with which readers can then build as they exploit linguistic analyses and glosses to explore how the original source works. Even when readers do not know the language and cannot even decipher the script, alignments can reveal striking patterns.

Hafez Farsi / English Word Alignment ▾Show unaligned tokens

الا يا ايها الساقى ادر كاسا و ناوها	1.1.1.1	1.1.1.1	Ho Saki , pass around and offer the bowl of love for God
که عشق آسان نمود اول ولى افتاد مشکلها	1.1.1.2	1.1.1.2	For the burden of love for God at first on the day of covenant appeared easy , but now difficulties have occurred .

[Figure 5](#): Words added to an English translation for the Persian poetry of Hafez

The figure above contains part of a manual alignment between the Persian poems of Hafez and a 19th century English translation that Maryam Foradi, then PI Crane's PhD student at Leipzig, manually produced as a part of her dissertation. This data was downloaded from the [Ugarit Alignment Editor](#) which Tariq Yousef created when he was also one of Crane's PhD students at Leipzig. Readers who place their mouse over the word "love," for example, see the corresponding Persian word. Words in the English that could not be aligned to anything in the Persian are highlighted. Readers who do not know Persian will immediately recognize the need for transliteration as well as linguistic explanation for the highlighted Persian term in order to go further.

الا يا ايها الساقى ادر كاسا و ناولها	1.1.1.1	1.1.1.1	Ho Saki , pass around and offer the bowl of love for God
که عشق آسان نمود اول ولی	1.1.1.2	1.1.1.2	For the burden of love for God at first on the day of covenant
افتاد مشکلها			appeared easy , but now difficulties have occurred .

[Figure 5a](#): Highlighting English words that cannot be aligned to the Persian.

The example above does, however, show what alignments can sometimes reveal, even when readers have no knowledge of the original language. All words that could not be aligned to the Persian are highlighted and the difference is striking. The translator has converted “bowl” into a “bowl of love for God.” “Love” in the third line of the English does in fact correspond to a Persian word but the words around it have been added so that “love” becomes “the burden of love for God.” The phrase “on the day of the covenant” has been added to “at first.” Only the addition of “now” towards the end is relatively innocuous.

Some translators leave out most of the epithets in Homer. Older translations of Greek and Latin regularly omit without comment references to sexuality. Some translations are so free that it is often impossible to create close alignments. These details, previously accessible only to those who knew the source language, can emerge very clearly.

The next figure illustrates a very different approach. Amelia Parrish (Tufts ‘21) worked on a born-digital aligned translation of *Odyssey*, book 5 as part of her undergraduate thesis. For the next two years, while she worked at a job saving money for law school, she added a translation of *Iliad* 1 and continued to work on the aligned translations and on commentary. She and PI Crane met almost every Saturday via Zoom until she moved to begin law school in summer 2023. Parrish and Crane went back over and over the text, exploring how best to produce a translation designed to lead into the Greek. The alignment shows, for example, that we have laboriously rendered the Greek imperfect middle verb *ōrnuth’* as “began to rouse herself,” with the “began to” emphasizing the fact that an imperfect indicates action over time and the “herself” illustrating the reflexive function of the Greek middle. Those who wish to read literary translations of Homer have an embarrassment of riches. This translation was designed for those who wish to compare a literary translation with the Greek and/or for learners of Ancient Greek who want to see reinforced in English the grammatical features that they are learning.

Odyssey Word Alignment ▼		Show unaligned tokens
5.1 Ἠώς δ' ἐκ λεχέων παρ' ἀγαυοῦ Τιθωνοῖο		5.1 Dawn, out of her bed from beside noble Tithonus,
5.2 ὤρνυθ', ἴν' ἀθανάτοισι φόως φέροι ἠδὲ βροτοῖσιν·		5.2 began to rouse herself, so that she might carry in light to the undying gods and to the mortal men.
5.3 οἱ δὲ θεοὶ θῶκόνδε καθίζανον, ἐν δ' ἄρα τοῖσι		5.3 The gods started to take their seats in their places, and among them then was

[Figure 6](#): Opening of a born-digital translation of *Odyssey* 5 by Amelia Parrish (Tufts '21).

When we look at the unaligned words in the figure below, the difference between the Parrish translation and that of the *Divan* becomes visible.

Odyssey Word Alignment ▼		Hide unaligned tokens
5.1 Ἠώς δ' ἐκ λεχέων παρ' ἀγαυοῦ Τιθωνοῖο		5.1 Dawn, out of her bed from beside noble Tithonus,
5.2 ὤρνυθ', ἴν' ἀθανάτοισι φόως φέροι ἠδὲ βροτοῖσιν·		5.2 began to rouse herself, so that she might carry in light to the undying gods and to the mortal men.
5.3 οἱ δὲ θεοὶ θῶκόνδε καθίζανον, ἐν δ' ἄρα τοῖσι		5.3 The gods started to take their seats in their places, and among them then was

[Figure 7](#): Unaligned words in Greek source and Parrish translation

Greek does not need to include possessive pronouns and thus we render “bed” as “her bed.” Subjects do not have to be expressed in Greek – Greek is a “pro-drop” language – and so we had to add “she.” Likewise, the word that becomes the definite article in Classical Greek is

almost always a pronoun in Homeric Greek and thus we have added “the” to “to the mortal men.” We can also quantify how often we do and do not have to add possessives, pronouns, and articles so that we can begin to compare Greek and English usage.

Systems such as Ugarit provide an elegant platform by which readers can align source text and translation, a task that students and instructors alike often experience more as a puzzle than a chore. Ugarit, however, assumes that text and translation are fixed and is not designed to deal with modifications to either. If annotators choose to revise their translations, they have to start the alignment over again. This is not a problem if annotators are aligning clean transcriptions of preexisting source texts and translations. It is also tolerable, though annoying, for students who align translations that they have produced themselves because they inevitably notice details during the alignment process that they missed in their initial work (this is one reason why translation alignment can be pedagogically valuable). Students quickly learn to pay close attention to the translation before they begin alignment (which is not a bad pedagogical outcome).

But if a translator expects to revise a translation over and over, restarting the alignment process is burdensome, if not prohibitive. We developed an inline format for alignment that allows us to modify text and alignment in an ongoing fashion.

Odyssey Book 5: Aligned Translation
Amelia Parrish, Gregory Crane

1. Dawn [Ἠὼς], out of[ἐκ] her[0] bed[λεχέων] from beside[παρ'] noble[ἀγαυοῦ]
Tithonus[Τιθωνοῖο],
2. began to rouse herself[she:ὄρνωθ'], so that[ἵν'] she[0] might carry[she:φέρει] light[φώως]
to[ἀθανάτοισι] the[0] undying[ἀθανάτοισι] gods[0] and[ἠδὲ] to mortals[βροτοῖσιν].
3. The[οἱ] gods[θεοὶ] started to take their seats[they:καθίζανον] in their places[θῶκόνδε], and[δ']
among[ἐν] them[τοῖσι] then [ἄρα] was[0]
4. Zeus[Ζεὺς], thunderer on high[ὕψιβρεμέτης], and[τε] whose[οῦ] power[κράτος] is[it: ἐστὶ] the[0]
greatest[μέγιστον].
5. To them[τοῖσι] Athena[Ἀθηναίη] began narrating[she:λέγει] the[0] many[πόλλ'] troubles[κίδεα]
of Odysseus[Ὀδυσῆος],
6. bringing these things to mind[μνησαμένη]- for[γάρ] he[0] was a concern[he:μέλει] to her[οἱ],

Figure 8: An inline format to represent alignment between translation and source text.

In the figure above, all text up to a Greek word in square brackets is that aligned with that Greek word. Where an English word has no equivalent in the Greek, a “[0]” follows it. Where a Greek word is not translated, it simply is left out (and will show up as an unaligned token).

<p>1.1 Bello Alexandrino conflato Caesar Rhoda atque ex Syria Ciliciaque omnem classem arcessit. Creta sagittarios, equites ab rege Nabataeorum Malcho euocat. Tormenta undique conquiri et frumentum mitti auxilia adduci iubet.</p>	<p>1.1 With the kindling of the Alexandrian War Caesar summoned his whole fleet from Rhodes and from Syria and Cilicia. He called up archers from Crete, cavalry from Malchus, king of the Nabataeans. He ordered siege engines to be collected from everywhere, grain to be sent, and reinforcements to be brought.</p>
---	--

Figure 9: Alignments between Latin and English added to the Damon *Bellum Alexandrinum*

Because the DLL publishes its editions under an open license, we were able to publish alignments produced by Valeria Boano of the Catholic University of Milan. The figure above shows the opening section (the rest of the alignments are in Ugarit and are being imported into Beyond Translation).

More recent advances in automatic alignment mean that the role of translation alignment – and the need to represent alignments in a reading environment – is poised to expand. David Bamman, then a researcher at Perseus, began our own work with translation alignment with an earlier NEH grant (50013-08) in 2008. He used an existing system, Giza++,⁴ that used preexisting bilingual corpora aligned at a chunk level (the smaller the chunking, the better). The results contained many errors but enough automatic alignments were correct that Bamman was able to use alignments to track features such as semantic change in corpora with millions of words. Thus, he could measure the frequency with which Latin oratio was translated into English as “prayer” vs. “speech” to track the rise of Christianity and then the emergence of a Classicizing humanism.⁵ The errors were all too numerous for anyone reading a text with these automatic alignments.

Tariq Yousef was able to exploit two resources not available to Bamman fifteen years ago. First, he had accumulated thousands of word-level alignments in Ugarit by trusted annotators. Second, language technologies have, of course, made major advances in the subsequent years. In particular, systems can now segment words into chunks, inferring the presence of endings and making parallel text alignment for highly inflected languages much more powerful. Tariq used the new data and methods to publish models for aligning Greek to English, Latin to English and Greek to Latin with accuracy of c. 80%, 80%, and 90% respectively. Automatic alignment is good enough that we can add it to our backend workflow for Perseus texts and make translation alignment available as a standard service in the reading environment (and not just where individuals have created a manual alignment).

⁴ Still in use, with code available at <https://github.com/moses-smt/giza-pp>.

⁵ Bamman 2008; Bamman 2011.

Finally, the new automatic alignment service also provides very usable starting materials for manual alignment. Annotators can begin with the preexisting alignments and only change what is necessary.

Trebanks: part of speech, regularized dictionary forms, and syntax

For the reader puzzling over precisely how a word in the source text functions linguistically, trebanks are the next stop.

Trebanks are textual corpora in which linguistic annotations describe each word. Typically, these annotations include the part of speech (e.g., “dative plural masculine”, “aorist 3rd singular indicative active”), the regularized dictionary form (e.g., *fecit*, “he/she/it did,” is an inflected form of *faciō*, “to do, make”), and syntactic role and dependency (e.g., in the first two words of the *Iliad*: *mênin aeide*, “sing [the] wrath!,” *mênin*, “wrath” is the object and it depends on *aeide*, “sing!”). Trebanks were developed by corpus linguists to support quantifiable research on linguistic corpora. We also use trebanks in Beyond Translation to explain the linguistic function of every word in a text.

PI Crane had wanted to develop syntactic databases of Greek and Latin in the 1980s but the technology was not yet in place. In 2002, however, Crane called for the development of a treebank for Ancient Greek ([Crane 2002](#)). In 2007, David Bamman submitted a successful proposal to the National Science Foundation that made it possible to begin work on a Latin Treebank. Bamman built the infrastructure and developed the annotation scheme in collaboration with Marco Passarotti of the Index Thomisticus. Soon afterwards support from the Alpheios Project allowed Perseus to begin work on a Greek treebank in 2008.

Fifteen years after active development began, we can now import and display treebank data in Beyond Translation for multiple languages (English, Greek, Latin, Arabic) and from multiple formats. The Perseus Dependency Treebank Scheme, which is closely based on the [Prague Dependency Treebank](#) format, is the legacy format developed in 2007. More than 1 million words of Greek, for example, are available under an open license in trebanks curated by manual annotators. These curated trebanks have been used to train models for machine learning that have been applied to generate automatic treebank data for more than 10 million words of Greek. More recently, the [Universal Dependencies](#) (UD) Framework has emerged. UD was designed precisely to facilitate cross language comparison. UD Treebanks have been used to train standard NLP pipelines such as Stanza and SpaCy. Ultimately, we need to convert Greek and Latin trebanks from the Perseus format to UD. For now, we can manage both formats.

The figure below is from one of the first two major trebanks for Ancient Greek (the other was a treebank for the New Testament produced by the Norwegian [Proiel Project](#)). Two students of Greek independently annotated each sentence. A more senior annotator (initially a postdoc, but later a undergraduate from Berkeley whose own treebanking had demonstrated her skill) checked places where the two annotators differed and finalized the annotation.

1.1-1.2 (2274106)

1.1	μῆνιν mênin μῆνις OBJ n-s---fa- Acc1. wrath, anger غضب	ἄειδε áeide ἀείδω PRED_CO v2spma--- Pres6. I Impr1. I Act1. to sing سرودن	θεά theà θεά ExD n-s---fv- Voc1. a goddess الهه، ایزدبانو	Πηληϊάδεω Pēlēiádeō Πηλείδης ATR n-s---mg- - - پور پلئوس	Ἀχιλλῆος Achilēos Ἀχιλλεύς ATR n-s---mg- Gen7. Achilles آخیلئوس
1.2	οὐλομένην ouloménēn οὐλόμενος ATR a-s---fa- - destructive, baneful ویرانگر	,	,	,	,
		AuxX u----- -			

Hide Translations

Sing, goddess, the godlike wrath of Achilles, son of Peleus, that sociopathic wrath

غضب آخیلئوس، پور پلئوس را بسرای، ای الهه؛

Figure 10: The opening of the *Iliad* in the Perseus Homer Treebank.

The display above resembles the token-level annotations described earlier. Multiple categories of data for each word are displayed: transliteration, inflected form from the text, lemma (regularized dictionary form), syntactic role, part of speech, grammatical category (where not obvious) and glosses – in both English and Persian. Translations for the sentence as a whole are displayed in English and Persian.

Here, however, the syntax provides a larger structuring force. As users mouse over words, not only are the words themselves highlighted but the word which governs it (never more than one word) is underlined in blue while the words that depend upon it are underlined in green. Thus, in “sing [the] godlike wrath of Achilles,” *mênin*, “wrath,” is the object of *aeide*, “sing,” which has blue underlining. Each word depends upon exactly one ancestor but can have an open ended

number of words depending on it. The adjective *oulomenên*, “sociopathic,” and the noun *Achileôs*, “of Achilles,” have blue underlining because they depend on *mênin*.

Hide Metadata

Figure 11: The syntactic structure presented as an inverted tree, with credits for this particular sentence

The figure above shows the more traditional method of visualizing syntactic structure as an inverted tree. Trees, however, can grow unwieldy in very large sentences (and Greek prose cultivates long, convoluted sentences with more than 100 words). Beyond Translation

collaborator James Tauber suggested the use of the in-line colored highlighting to get around the complexity of a tree. We offer both methods of visualization, inline and structured as a tree.

1

μήνιν	ἄειδε	θεὰ	Πηληϊάδεω	Ἀχιλλῆος	οὐλομένην	,	ἧ	μυρί'	Ἀχαιοῖς	ἄλγε'
mēnīn	áeide	theà	Pēlēiádeō	Achilēos	ouloménēn	,	hè	myrí'	Achairois	álge'
μήνης	αἰίδω	θεά	Πηληϊάδης	Ἀχιλλεύς	οὐλόμενος	,	ὅς	μυρίος	Ἀχαιός	ἄλγος
obj	root	vocative	nmod	nmod	amod	punct	nsubj	amod	iobj	obj
NOUN	VERB	NOUN	PROPN	PROPN	ADJ	PUNCT	PRON	ADJ	ADJ	NOUN
ἔθηκε	,	πολλάς	δ'	ἰφθίμους	ψυχὰς	Ἄϊδι	προΐαψεν	ἠρώων	,	αὐτούς
éthēke	,	pollàs	d'	iphthímous	psychàs	Áidi	proíapsen	hērōōn	,	autoús
τίθημι	,	πολύς	δέ	ἴφθιμος	ψυχή	Ἄιδης	προιάπτω	ἠρως	,	αὐτός
acl:reicl	punct	amod	cc	amod	obj	iobj	conj	nmod	punct	obj
VERB	PUNCT	ADJ	CCONJ	ADJ	NOUN	PROPN	VERB	NOUN	PUNCT	PRON

Figure 12: A Universal Dependency version of the Homer Treebank.

The figure above simply shows the [Daphne Homeric Treebank](#). This was derived originally from the Perseus Homer Treebank). Francesco Mambrini (who created the Perseus treebanks for Aeschylus and Sophocles) converted it to UDF and has been augmenting it.

orcid.org/0009-0003-2791-1365

Expand All Trees

Lemma Relationship Morph. Tag

1

Bello Alexandrino conflato Caesar Rhodo atque ex Syria Cilicia que omnem classem arcessit .

Hide Tree

Figure 13: Treebanks added to the Damon edition of the *Bellum Alexandrinum*

Because the DLL publishes its data under a Creative Commons license and Beyond Translation thus could upload that work, Valeria Boano of the Catholic University of Milan was able to create a treebank for the Damon edition of the *Bellum Alexandrinum* and to publish it in Beyond Translation. We thus have an alternate version of the edition that offers features that the DLL has chosen not to include – in no small measure precisely because they knew that publishing under an open license meant that others could do so.

Figure 14: Treebank of an English translation of the life of Omar ben Saeed.

The figure above presents the UD treebank for the English translation of *The Life of Omar ben Saeed*, a West African kidnapped into slavery in the US who published his autobiography in Arabic. Joseph Hilleary at Tufts led a group that translated and edited the Arabic. The goal is to publish treebanks of the Arabic and the English so that we can highlight differences in the structure of the languages.

Annotations to language specific grammars and lexica

Neither Perseus 3 (written primarily in Perl by David Smith starting in 1995) nor Perseus 4 (written primarily in Java by David Mimno starting in 2003) made it possible to highlight annotated words. There were already too many dictionaries, commentaries, grammars and other reference works that cited texts in Perseus and we chose not to deal with the messy problem of managing many overlapping annotations. Beyond Translation returned to this problem. The architecture that allows us to link spans in a source text with textual notes can be used in other contexts.

- 1.1.1 Θουκυδίδης Αθηναῖος **ξυνέγραψε** τὸν πόλεμον τῶν Πελοποννησίων καὶ Αθηναίων, **ὡς ἐπολέμησαν** πρὸς ἀλλήλους, **ἀρξάμενος** εὐθύς **καθισταμένου** καὶ **ἐλπίσας** μέγαν τε ἔσσεσθαι καὶ **ἀξιολογώτατον** τῶν προγεγενημένων, **τεκμαιρόμενος** ὅτι ἀκμάζοντες **τε ἦσαν** ἐς αὐτὸν ἀμφοτέροι παρασκευῇ τῇ πάσῃ καὶ τὸ **ἄλλο Ἑλληνικὸν ὄρων** ξυνιστάμενον πρὸς ἑκατέρους, τὸ μὲν εὐθύς, τὸ δὲ **καὶ διανοοῦμενον**.
- 1.1.2 κίνησις γὰρ αὕτη μεγίστη δὴ τοῖς Ἑλλήσιν ἐγένετο καὶ μέρει τινὶ τῶν βαρβάρων, ὡς δὲ εἶπειν καὶ ἐπὶ πλεῖστον ἀνθρώπων.

→

COMMENTARY

Θουκυδίδης

ξυνέγραψε
ξυνέγραψε—a characteristic word of Thuc., who is known to the ancient critics as ὁ συγγραφεύς, much as Homer is ὁ ποιητής. It denotes the bringing together in one work of many occurrences—composing in its etymological sense. (How some find a reference to the hunting up of materials is not clear.)

ὡς ἐπολέμησαν
ἀρξάμενος (τοῦ ξυνοῦσθαι) κτλ

Figure 15: A traditional commentary (Marchant on the opening of Thucydides).

The figure above shows a standard commentary (in this case, E. A. Marchant’s 1905 commentary on Book 1 of Thucydides). This is essentially the same service as was used for the textual notes and shows the generality of this annotation display service. The following two figures show how this general service can be expanded.

- 1.1 μῆνιν ἄειδε θεὰ Πηληϊάδεω Ἀχιλῆος
- 1.2 οὐλομένην, ἣ μυρὶ Ἀχαιοῖς ἄλγε’ ἔθηκε,
- 1.3 πολλὰς δ’ ἰφθίμους ψυχὰς Ἄϊδι προΐαψεν
- 1.4 ἠρώων, αὐτοὺς δὲ ἑλώρια τεύχε κύνεσσιν
- 1.5 οἰωνοῖσι τε πᾶσι, Διὸς δ’ ἐτελείετο βουλή,
- 1.6 ἐξ οὗ δὴ τὰ πρῶτα διαστήτην ἐρίσαντε
- 1.7 Ἀτρεΐδης τε ἀναξ ἀνδρῶν καὶ δῖος Ἀχιλλεύς.
- 1.8 τίς τ’ ἄρ σφωε θεῶν ἕριδι ξυνέηκε μάχεσθαι;
- 1.9 Δητοῦς καὶ Διὸς υἱός· ὃ γὰρ βασιλῆϊ χολωθεῖς
- 1.10 νοῦσον ἀνὰ στρατὸν ὄρσε κακίην, ὀλέκοντο δὲ λαοί,
- 1.11 οὔνεκα τὸν Χρῦσῃν ἠτίμασεν ἀρητήτρα
- 1.12 Ἀτρεΐδης· ὃ γὰρ ἦλθε θεὸς ἐπὶ νῆας Ἀχαιῶν
- 1.13 λυσόμενός τε θύγατρα φέρων τ’ ἀπερείσι’ ἄποινα,
- 1.14 στέμματ’ ἔχων ἐν χερσὶν ἐκηβόλου Ἀπόλλωνος
- 1.15 χρυσέῳ ἀνὰ σκήπτρῳ, καὶ λίσσετο πάντας Ἀχαιοῦς,
- 1.16 Ἀτρεΐδα δὲ μάλιστα δῶω, κοσμήτορε λαῶν·
- 1.17 Ἀτρεΐδαι τε καὶ ἄλλοι εὐκνήμιδες Ἀχαιοί,
- 1.18 ὑμῖν μὲν θεοὶ δοῖεν Ὀλύμπια δώματ’ ἔχοντες
- 1.19 ἐκπέρσαι Πριάμοιο πόλιν, εὖ δ’ οἴκαδ’ ἰκέσθαι·
- 1.20 παῖδα δ’ ἐμοὶ λύσαιτε φίλην, τὰ δ’ ἄποινα δέχεσθαι,

From the *Didakta Modular Grammar* by Farnoosh Shamsian

→

GRAMMATICAL ENTRIES

Aor2. Ingressive Aorist
Dat1. Complement of the verb
Dat2. Possessor
Dat6. Manner and means
Gen1. Possessor
Gen2. Partitive
Gen7. Subjective
Gen8. Objective

Impf1. Imperfect of Continuance x

The imperfect represents an action as ongoing in the past.

→ “διέφθειραν Ἀθηναίων πέντε καὶ εἴκοσι, οἱ ξυνοπολιορκούντο” T. 3.68; → they put to death twenty-five of the Athenians who were besieged (i.e. from the beginning to the end of the siege)

→ “ἐβασίλευεν Ἀντίοχος” T. 2.80; → Antiochus was reigning

The imperfect of verbs of sending, going, saying, exhorting, etc., which imply continuous action, is often used where one might expect the aorist of concluded action. Thus, in ἔπεμpton, the action is regarded as unfinished since the goal is not reached.

→ “ἀγγελον ἔπεμπον καὶ τοὺς νεκροὺς ὑποσπόνδους ἀπέδωσαν” T. 2.6; → they sent a messenger and surrendered the dead under a truce

Figure 16: Annotations and the Didakta Modular Grammar.

In the figure above, highlighted words have annotations keyed to the *Didakta Modular Grammar* (on which, see below).

In the figure above, a reader has clicked on one of the words in green because all four words have been tagged as exhibiting the “imperfect of continuance,” i.e., in each case, we have judged that the verbs emphasize the duration of an event. In line 4, the murderous wrath of Achilles “kept making over a period of time” (*teuche*) the heroes into objects to be seized by dogs and birds. In highlighting all words with a shared grammatical annotation, we help readers see which features show up repeatedly.

The right hand side shows the subset of the grammar relevant to this particular passage. It jumps from Genitive 2 to Genitive 7 because Genitives 3, 4, 5, and 6 do not appear in this section of Greek.

The screenshot displays the Iliad text in Greek with a dropdown menu for selecting a dictionary. The text is as follows:

1.1 μῆνιν ἄειδε θεὰ Πηληϊάδεω
 1.2 οὐλομένην, ἣ μυρὶ Ἀχαιοῖς
 1.3 πολλὰς δ' ἰφθίμους ψυχὰς Ἄ
 1.4 ἥρώων, αὐτοὺς δὲ ἐλώρια τ
 1.5 οἰωνοῖσι τε πάσι, Διὸς δ' ἔτε
 1.6 ἔξ οὔ δὴ τὰ πρῶτα διαστήτη
 1.7 Ἀτρεΐδης τε ἄναξ ἀνδρῶν κ
 1.8 τίς τ' ἄρ σφωε θεῶν ἔριδι ξ
 1.9 Δητοῦς καὶ Διὸς υἱός· ὃ γὰρ βασιλῆϊ χολωθεῖς
 1.10 νοῦσον ἀνὰ στρατὸν ὄρσε κακῆν, ὀλέκοντο δὲ λαοί,
 1.11 οὐνεκα τὸν Χρῦσσην ἠτίμασεν ἀρητῆρα
 1.12 Ἀτρεΐδης· ὃ γὰρ ἦλθε θοάς ἐπὶ νῆας Ἀχαιῶν
 1.13 λυσόμενός τε θύγατρα φέρων τ' ἀπερείσι' ἄποινα,
 1.14 στέμματ' ἔχων ἐν χερσίν ἐκηβόλου Ἀπόλλωνος
 1.15 χρυσέῳ ἀνὰ σκήπτρῳ, καὶ λίσσετο πάντας Ἀχαιοῦς,
 1.16 Ἀτρεΐδα δὲ μάλιστα δῶν, κοσμήτορε λαῶν·
 1.17 Ἀτρεΐδα τε καὶ ἄλλοι εὐκνήμιδες Ἀχαιοί,
 1.18 ὕμῖν μὲν θεοὶ δοῖεν Ὀλύμπια δώματ' ἔχοντες
 1.19 ἐκπέρσαι Πριάμοιο πόλιν, εὖ δ' οἴκαδ' ἰκέσθαι·
 1.20 παῖδα δ' ἐμοὶ λύσατε φίλην, τὰ δ' ἄποινα δέχεσθαι.

The dropdown menu shows the following options:

- All Dictionaries
- Cambridge Greek Lexicon
- Cunliffe (Homperers)
- Cunliffe (Lex Entries)
- Lexicon
- Thucydideum
- LSJ

The dictionary entry for 'κύων' is shown on the right:

κύων
 κύων κυνός *m.f.* | VOC. ΚΥΩΝ DAT.PL. ΚΥΩΙ
 EP. ΚΥΩΕΣΣΙ |
 1 dog, bitch, hound Hom.
 2 (in oaths, esp. as sworn by Socrates) νῆορ μᾶττον κύνα by the dog Ar. Pl.
 3 (as a contemptuous term for a shameless person, esp. a woman) dog, bitch Hom.
 4 (as a mythol. creature or attendant of a deity) hound (pl., w.GEN. of Madness) E. (pl., ref. to Erinyes) Trag. (fig., ref. to the Sphinx, the Hydra) S. E. (w.GEN. of Zeus, ref. to an eagle, griffin, Harpy) A. AR. (of Cybele, ref. to Pan) Pl./fr.
 5 (fig., ref. to a person) watchdog, guard-dog (sts. w.GEN. of a place) A. Ar. (w.GEN. of the people, ref. to a politician) D. Thphr.
 6 (w.art., ref. to Diogenes) the Dog, the Cynic Arist.
 7 dog (w.GEN. of Orion, ref. to the dog-star; i.e. Sirius) II. (w.ADJ. σείριος) A. (without GEN.ADJ.) Arist. Plb.
 8 a kind of marine animal; perh. dogfish, shark Od.

Figure 17: Varying coverage of a given text (here the *Iliad*) by multiple lexica.

Beyond Translation currently includes six Greek dictionaries (with more to come). The two Cunliffe lexica cover the vocabulary of Homer (Lex Entries) and proper names (Homperers). A specialized lexicon for Greek-Latin Thucydides is available, with English translations added. We also include the Liddell Scott Greek English lexicon (first digitized by Perseus with NEH support in the 1990s). The default lexicon is the new *Cambridge Greek Lexicon*, the first rights-restricted resource that Perseus has added in twenty years. We are able to include this because Jeff Rydberg-Cox, then a postdoc at Perseus, negotiated the rights for Perseus in exchange for his support building infrastructure to help write the lexicon. Our default setting is to present the new *Cambridge Greek Lexicon*, but readers can select from any of the six.

In this case, we do more than just label annotated words. “Cited” indicates that one of the available dictionaries comments on this particular word in this particular passage. “Available” indicates that one or more dictionaries has an entry for a word. “Missing” (of which there are none in this passage) indicates words for which none of the available dictionaries have an entry.

Named Entity Linking and Mapping

While working as chief developer at Perseus before going on to earn his PhD, David A. Smith began working on named entity classification (does “Alexandria” in a given passage describe a person or a place?) and named entity linking (Alexandria, VA? Alexandria in Egypt?). Perseus 3 applied named entity linking to automatically tag place names in its English translations with the Getty Gazetteer. We then allowed readers to generate maps of places mentioned on the page they were viewing. The named entity linking was automatic and contained errors but the maps were helpful and others (such as the [Hestia Project](#)) created more refined data by correcting the automatic annotations. The [ToposText Project](#) downloaded millions of words of English translations (including those from Perseus) and created curated annotations. The particular focus was linking place names to its own gazetteer (but with links to the [Pleiades Gazetteer](#) wherever possible). The [Recogito Geotagging Widget](#) facilitates linking of place names in Greek and Latin sources in the original languages with the Pleiades Gazetteer.

A great deal of work has thus gone into linking named entities from primary sources to authority lists. Most work has focused on tagging place names but ToposText has done substantial work linking people to Wikidata entries. We have updated our automatic mapping services.

ODYSSEY (GREEK TEXT OF MURRAY)

3.159 ἐς Τένεδον δ' ἐλθόντες ἐρέξαμεν ἱρὰ θεοῖσιν,
 3.160 οἴκαδε ἰέμενοι· Ζεὺς δ' οὐ πω μῆδετο νόστον,
 3.161 σκέτλιος, ὃς ῥ' ἔριν ὤρσε κακὴν ἐπι δεῦτερον αὐτίς.
 3.162 οἱ μὲν ἀποστρέψαντες ἔβαν νέας ἀμφιπέλοισα
 3.163 ἄμφ' Ὀδυσῆα ἄνακτα δαΐφρονα, ποικιλομήτην,
 3.164 αὐτίς ἐπ' Ἀτρεΐδῃ Ἀγαμέμνονι ἦρα φέροντες·
 3.165 αὐτὰρ ἐγὼ σὺν νηυσὶν ἀολκείαιν, αἶ μοι ἔποντο,
 3.166 φεῖγον, ἐπεὶ γίνωσκον, ὃ δὴ κακὰ μῆδετο δαίμων.
 3.167 φεῖγε δὲ Τυδέος υἱὸς ἄρηιος, ὥρσε δ' ἑταίρους.
 3.168 ὄψε δὲ δὴ μετὰ νῶϊ κίε Ξανθοῦ Μενέλαος,
 3.169 ἐν Ἀέσβῳ δ' ἔκικεν δολιχὸν πλόον ὀρμαίνοντα,
 3.170 ἢ καθύπερθε Χίοιο νεοίμεθα παιπαλοέσσης,
 3.171 νήσου ἐπὶ Ψυρῆς, αὐτὴν ἐπ' ἀριστερ' ἔχοντες,
 3.172 ἧ ὑπένερθε Χίοιο, παρ' ἠνεμόεντα Μίμαντα.
 3.173 ἦτέομεν δὲ θεὸν φῆναι τέρας· αὐτὰρ ὃ γ' ἡμῖν
 3.174 δεῖξε, καὶ ἠνώγει πέλαγος μέσον εἰς Εὐβοίαν
 3.175 τέμνειν, ὄφρα τάχιστα ὑπέκ κακότητα φύγοιμεν.
 3.176 ὦρτο δ' ἐπὶ λιγῶς οὖρος ἀήμενα· αἶ δὲ μάλ' ὤκα
 3.177 ἰχθυόεντα κέλευθα διέδραμον, ἐς δὲ Τεραστὸν

Chios (island)

NAMED ENTITIES

- Menelaus
- Agamemnon
- Tenedos (island)
- Diomedes
- Lesbos (island)
- Chios (island)
- Chios is the fifth largest of the Greek islands.
- Read More
- Psyra (island)
- Mimas (mountain)
- Euboea (island)

Figure 18: a map of locations mentioned in book 3 of the *Odyssey*

The figure above shows named entities annotated in *Odyssey*. The reader has selected Chios and the name of the island appears in a pop up in a larger map, while its entry on the right side bar shows a detailed view. Joshua Kemp (Furman '23) used [Recogito to generate the named entity annotations](#) for the Greek text of the *Odyssey*.

Adding visualizations of meter and sound recordings

Some who have learned how to read meters such as dactylic hexameters or iambic trimeters at sight and who never write the scansion may forget how hard it is for those engaging with Greek to treat poetry as poetry – and not as a series of linguistic linear equations to be solved. We can not only visualize the metrical structure of individual lines of poetry but also provide an accompanying recording of someone reading each line. We are not yet to the point where we can highlight each word as it is spoken (as some [Music Encoding Initiative](#) readers can highlight notes as they are played) but the system is still effective. PI Crane requires his students reading Homer in English translation to listen to the Beyond Translation data for the first seven lines of the *Iliad* and then to record themselves reading it. Usually a bit shocked at first, students are all able to perform reasonably well. Some read the hexameters with such fluency that it is hard to believe they have not studied Ancient Greek. All begin to experience the *Iliad*, at least a bit, as poetry.

Perhaps the greatest individual contribution to the study of Greek and Latin in a digital age is the publication of scans for more than 250,000 individual lines of Greek and Latin poetry. David Chamberlain not only created the scans but built a site to publish them in an attractive interface. And on top of that, he published his data under an open license. And on top of that as well, Chamberlain also published a smaller, but substantial, collection of digitized recordings as he reads Homeric poetry in fully tonal Ancient Greek.

The screenshot displays a digital interface for the Iliad. On the left, the Greek text of the opening lines (1.1-1.20) is shown with metrical annotations. Syllables are color-coded: long syllables are in a darker gray, and short syllables are in a lighter gray. Vertical bars (|) indicate regular metrical units, and dotted bars (|·) indicate caesuras. On the right, a control panel includes a play button for audio, a 'TEXT WIDTH' dropdown menu (set to 'Narrow'), a 'DISPLAY MODE' dropdown menu (set to 'Default'), and a 'GRAMMATICAL ENTRIES' list with various options like 'Acc1. Direct Object' and 'Acc10. Double Accusative'. The interface is titled 'ILIAD (GREEK TEXT OF MUNRO & ALLEN)'.

Figure 19: A visualization of the meter and linked recording of the opening lines of the *Iliad*.

In the figure above long syllables are a darker gray, short syllables a lighter gray. The regular divisions between regular metrical units are represented by a solid vertical bar (|) while a dotted bar indicates a break (caesura) within a metrical unit. The button below “Audio” in the right hand column begins a recording of the lines on the page.

Linking transcriptions to details on the page: the Homer Multitext

We can use the International Image Interchange Framework (<https://iiif.io/>) to integrate textual transcriptions and high resolution images of their material sources (papyri, manuscripts, printed books etc.). This not only allows readers of the manuscript (or other sources) to see a transcription but also to use all the other annotations that may be available (aligned translation, treebanks, etc.) to work with that source.

We were able to use a major project about Homer as our initial case. The [Homer Multitext Project](#) (HMT) is producing diplomatic editions of key manuscripts of Homer and the medieval scholia that they contain. After more than a decade of work, HMT completed an edition of the Venetus A, a 10th century CE Byzantine manuscript and probably the most important single source for ancient scholarship about the Homeric epics. Where the text of the *Iliad* contains c. 115,000 running words, the six categories of scholia preserved in the Venetus A contain more than 400,000 words.

We used three publications from the HMT. First, the HMT published openly licensed high resolution images of the Venetus A. As part of a Mellon-funded collaboration with the Johns Hopkins Sheridan Libraries⁶ the images were added to its IIIF server and this made it possible to interact with them via the standard IIIF API. Second, they published TEI XML diplomatic editions of both the *Iliad* as it appears in the Venetus A and for each of the six categories of annotation. Third, they published the coordinates linking details of images to each transcription.

ILIAD (VENETUS A (MARCIANA 454 = 822), FOLIOS

12r.1.1 Μῆνιν ἄειδε θεὰ Πηληϊάδεω Ἀχιλῆος
12r.1.2 οὐλομένην· ἣ μυρὶ Ἀχαιοῖς ἄλγε' ἔθηκεν·
12r.1.3 πολλὰς δ' ἰφθίμους ψυχὰς Ἄϊδι προΐαφεν
12r.1.4 ἠρώων· αὐτοὺς δὲ ἐλώρια τεύχε κύνεσσιν
12r.1.5 οἰωνοῖσι τε πᾶσι· Διὸς δ' ἔτελειετο βουλή·
12r.1.6 ἔξ οὗ δ' ἅ τ' ἀπὸ πρῶτα διαστήτην ἐρίσαντε
12r.1.7 **Ἀτρεΐδης τε ἄναξ ἀνδρῶν καὶ δῖος Ἀχιλλεύς·**
12r.1.8 τίς τάρ σφωε θεῶν ἕριδι ξυνέηκε μάχεσθαι·
12r.1.9 Λητοῦς καὶ Διὸς υἱός· ὃ γὰρ βασιλῆϊ χλωθεῖς
12r.1.10 νοῦσον ἀνά στρατὸν ἄρσε κακῆν· ὀλέκοντο δὲ λαοί·
12r.1.11 οὔνεκα τὸν Χρῦσῆν ἠτίμασεν ἀρητήρα
12r.1.12 Ἀτρεΐδης· ὃ γὰρ ἦλθε θοάς ἐπὶ νῆας Ἀχαιῶν·
12r.1.13 λυσόμενός τε θήατρα· φέρον τ' ἀπερείσι' ἄποινα·
12r.1.14 στέμματα' ἔχων ἐν χερσίν ἐκηβόλου Ἀπόλλωνος
12r.1.15 χρῆσέω ἀνά σκήπτρῳ· καὶ λίσσετο πάντας Ἀχαιοῦς·
12r.1.16 Ἀτρεΐδα δὲ μάλιστα δύω κοσμήτορε λαῶν·
12r.1.17 Ἀτρεΐδαι τε καὶ ἄλλοι εὐκνήμιδες Ἀχαιοί·
12r.1.18 ἤμιν μὲν θεοὶ δοῖεν Ὀλύμπια δώματ' ἔχοντες
12r.1.19 ἐκπέρσαι Πριάμοιο πόλιν· εὐ δ' οἴκαδ' ἰκέσθαι·
12r.1.20 παῖδα δ' ἔμοι λύσασαι φίλην· τὰ δ' ἄποινα δεχέσθαι·
12r.1.21 ἄζήμενοι Διὸς υἱὸν ἐκηβόλου Ἀπόλλωνα·
12r.1.22 Ἔνθ' ἄλλοι μὲν πάντες ἐπευφήμησαν Ἀχαιοί·
12r.1.23 κιδεΐσθαι θ' ἰσοῖα καὶ ἀνιλέν δύνθαι ἄποινα·

SCHOLIA
φασὶν ἄρα μὴ μῆνας ἀπὸ τοῦ Ἰλίου πύργου ἀλλ' ἀπὸ χρόνου ἐγένετο ἡ μῆνις ἵνα μὴ τὰ παρὰ τοῖς νεωτέροις πλάσματα δεξόμεθα :

■ **Ἀτρεΐδης τε ἄναξ**
Ἀγαμέμνων κατὰ μὲν Ὅμηρον Ἀτρεΐος τοῦ Πέλοπος· μητρὸς δὲ Ἀερόπ, κατὰ δὲ Ηοιοῦ Πηλεΐθηνος, τὸ γένος Μυκηνάιος, ὃς ἤγαγε ναῦς εἰς Ἴλιον· ἐκ πορθήσας δὲ τὴν Ἴλιον, καὶ ὑποστρέψας οἴκαδ' ἀναίρει ὑπο Αἰγίσθου τοῦ Θυάστου δόλιφ ἐπι εὐωχίας οὗτος γὰρ παρὰ τὸν καιρὸν τῆς ἀποδομῆς εμοιχευσε τὴν Ἀγαμέμνονος γυναῖκα Κλυταμνήστραν κατὰ δὲ τοὺς τραγικούς αὐτὴν τὴν Κλυταμνήστραν ἀνελεῖν αὐτὸν χίτωνά μὴ ἔχοντα διεκδύειν τραχήλου· ἔσχεν δὲ ἐξ αὐτῆς ἢ μὲν Ὀρεσθῆν καὶ θυγατέρας τέσσαρας· Λοδί Χρυσὸθ Ἰργιμένην καὶ Ἠλέκτραν :

■ **Λητοῦς καὶ Διὸς υἱός**
ερασθεῖς Λητοῦς τῆς Κόιου θνηταὸς ἐνὸς τῶν Τιτάνων καὶ

⁶ “A Framework for Annotation Interoperability.” <https://www.mellon.org/grant-details/a-framework-for-annotation-interoperability-20444975>

[Figure 20](#): *Iliad* 1.7 transcribed text and medieval annotation (left and right) with their location on the manuscript highlighted (center).

In the figure above, selecting line *Iliad* 1.7 generates highlights over the transcriptions of that line and any marginal annotations associated with it. Selecting *Iliad* 1.7 also highlights the sections of the manuscript page in which *Iliad* 1.7. The user interaction, here as elsewhere in Beyond Translation, still needs to be refined. As of this writing, readers would, for example, have to scroll down through the many items in the right hand widget to find the annotation shown above. Nevertheless, we can link transcription and source image.

The ability to link details of a scanned manuscript (or papyrus or inscription or book) to a network of explanatory annotations transforms the potential role of the manuscript. Experts in Greek and Latin may easily be able to connect the image of a manuscript page to the various scholarly resources about the text it contains but few of them would be able to do the same if presented with a manuscript page of the Persian *Shahnameh* or the Old French *Roman de la Rose*.

Integration with the Open Commentary Platform

Beyond Translation can in real time import annotations in natural language about any CTS citation (e.g., about *Iliad* 1.1 or about spans such as *Iliad* 1.1-1.10) from the New Alexandria Foundation's Open Commentary Platform (OCP). Each annotation has individual credits. The OCP provides a strategic service relevant to every annotation class in Beyond Translation. Every annotation task above involves many critical decisions that need explanation. We can use the OCP to include these explanations in a consistent format and in a single platform.

We accomplished OCP integration, a year before we began work on Beyond Translation in 2019 (Crane 2018). Beyond Translation has, however, allowed us to deepen the collaboration with the Open Commentary Platform (OCP), with increasingly coordinated development. A new version of the OCP is being completed and this will make it easier to import comments from traditional forms such as Microsoft Word.

9.300 εἰ δέ τοι Ἀτρεΐδης μὲν ἀπήχθετο κηρόθι μάλλον
 9.301 αὐτὸς καὶ τοῦ δῶρα, σὺ δ' ἄλλους περ Παναχαιοὺς
 9.302 τειρομένους ἐλέαιρε κατὰ στρατόν, οἷ σε θεὸν ὦς
 9.303 τίσουσ'· ἧ γάρ κέ σφι μάλα μέγα κῦδος ἄροιο·
 9.304 νῦν γάρ χ' Ἔκτορ' ἔλοις, ἐπεὶ ἂν μάλα τοι σχεδὸν
 ἔλθοι
 9.305 λύσσαν ἔχων ὀλοήν, ἐπεὶ οὐ τινά φησιν ὁμοῖον
 9.306 οἷ ἔμμενοι Δαναῶν οὐς ἐνθάδε νῆες ἔνεικαν.
 9.307 τὸν δ' ἀπαμειβόμενος προσέφη πόδας ὠκὺς
 Ἀχιλλεύς·
 9.308 διογενὲς Λαερτιάδη πολυμήχαν' Ὀδυσσεῦ
 9.309 χρῆ μὲν δὴ τὸν μῦθον ἀπηλεγέως ἀποειπεῖν,
 9.310 ἧ περ δὴ φρονέω τε καὶ ὦς τετελεσμένον ἔσται,
 9.311 ὥς μὴ μοι τρύζητε παρήμνοι ἄλλοθεν ἄλλος.
 9.312 ἐχθρὸς γάρ μοι κεῖνος ὁμῶς Αἴδαο πύλῃσιν
 9.313 ὃς χ' ἕτερον μὲν κεύθη ἐνὶ φρεσίν, ἄλλο δὲ εἶπη.
 9.314 αὐτὰρ ἐγὼν ἐρέω ὥς μοι δοκεῖ εἶναι ἄριστα·
 9.315 οὔτ' ἔμεγ' Ἀτρεΐδην Ἀγαμέμνονα πεισέμεν οἴω
 9.316 οὔτ' ἄλλους Δαναοὺς, ἐπεὶ οὐκ ἄρα τις χάρις ἦεν
 9.317 μάρνασθαι δηΐοισιν ἐπ' ἀνδράσι νωλεμέσ αἰεὶ.
 9.318 ἴση μοῖρα μένοντι καὶ εἰ μάλα τις πολεμίζοι·
 9.319 ἐν δὲ ἱὴ τιμῇ ἡμὲν κακὸς ἦδ' ἐκαὶ ἐσθλός·
 9.320 κάτθαν' ὁμῶς ὅ τ' ἀεργὸς ἀνήρ ὃ τε πολλὰ ἐοργάς.

NEW ALEXANDRIA
 COMMENTARY

Iliad 9.308-311

Greg Nagy

In these four verses, Achilles begins his own speech in response to the speech of Odysseus, and he rejects straightaway Agamemnon's offer for compensation. The tone is hostile toward Odysseus, not only toward Agamemnon.

Iliad 9.308-9.314

David Elmer

comparison of Plato's text of the verses with what has come down to us through the medieval manuscript tradition in the context of analyzing Socrates' and Hippias' debate over Homer's representation of Achilles

Iliad 9.308-9.429

Leonard Muelner

analysis of Achilles' response to Odysseus' speech in terms of his alienation, mēnis, desire to realize his heroic identity and win kleos, as well as the hostility between Achilles and Odysseus

Iliad 9.312-9.313

Douglas Frame

analysis of passages in the Iliad that (can) allude to the Odyssey, with these lines as an example anticipating O.14.156-157

Fig 21: Annotations by multiple authors in a passage of the *Iliad*.

Other Outputs

The Didakta Modular Grammar: Produced in cooperation with Beyond Translation by Farnoosh Shamsian. Farnoosh's PhD work is on using technology to help Persian speakers learn ancient Ancient Greek. Although Greek sources are very important for the study of ancient Persian history, very few resources exist in Persian about Ancient Greek and most translations into Persian are translations of translations from Greek into languages such as English and French. Farnoosh needed a compact grammar that she could localize for Persian speakers. Didakta used Smyth's Greek Grammar as its starting point, with revisions based on more modern resources such as the *Cambridge Greek Lexicon*.

Born-digital aligned translations from Persian to Greek and Kurdish: Farnoosh and her students have also published a translation of *Iliad* 1 into Persian (visible in the figures above) and Kurdish (available on [Zenodo](#)) as well as three separate translations of the Crito of Plato (available as a spreadsheet [here](#)). These are not only the first aligned translations into Persian and Kurdish but also the first direct translations from Greek into these languages.

Visualizations for Homeric Greek:

- [“Visualizing Progress in Homeric Greek \(1\),”](#)
- [“Visualizing progress in a historical language \(2\),”](#)
- [“Homeric Vocabulary, Heaps' Law and the open-ended nature of epic tradition,”](#)
- [“Attested Repetition in Homeric Epic.”](#)

Progress towards digital editions for textbooks on Ancient Greek and Classical Persian:

- Pharr's Homeric Greek: working TEI XML draft:
<https://github.com/gregorycrane/Homerica/blob/master/pharr.homgramm.xml>.
- Crosby and Schaeffer, An Introduction to Greek:
 - <https://github.com/gregorycrane/CrosbySchaeffer2.0/blob/main/crosbycschaeffer2.0.xml>
 - [Exercises \(one sheet per lesson\) with answers](#)
 - [Vocabulary with totals for the Anabasis](#).
- Italo Pizzi's grammar of the Persian of Ferdowsi
 - The glossary:
<https://github.com/gregorycrane/Shahnameh/blob/master/pizzi-glossary.it.xml>,
 - Persian Readings:
<https://github.com/gregorycrane/Shahnameh/blob/master/pizzi-readings.fa.xml>.
 - Pizzi's literal translations:
<https://github.com/gregorycrane/Shahnameh/blob/master/pizzi.littrans.txt>.

Other materials in preparation: We have Arabic and Persian content to add; treebanking and alignments for later Greek, sentence level alignments, glossaries and notes for Xenophon, etc.

5. Project Evaluation and Impact

We were successful in our primary goal of creating a single environment in which we could represent as many different classes as possible. We [published a largely feature complete version of Beyond Translation on March 15, 2023](#) so that we could solicit feedback to which we could respond in the final six months of work (March through August). We used the Perseus Blog, Twitter/X and Facebook to disseminate our work in an ongoing fashion. The feedback that we received was largely positive and we spent most of our effort adding content.

Because we have been developing Perseus for more than thirty years and because we had a clear idea of what we wanted to accomplish, we did not experience any major surprises (other than the fact that everything somehow always takes more time than we would wish). We would have hoped to have added more content to Beyond Translation by now but we do have the framework to which Perseus staff members should be able to add going forward.

Two surprises do, however, stand out. **First**, we had not appreciated the scope and vitality of the projects from various countries contributing open data about the Greco-Roman world and even just about Homer. We knew about virtually every project upon which we drew before we began. What we did not appreciate until we began to dig into the work was precisely how broad and rich the available data had become. Even individual projects within this landscape are not in a position to appreciate how dynamic and rich this new open data ecosystem already has become. We are doubly happy to have begun work on ways to pull together data from multiple

projects to fashion a whole that is greater than the sum of its parts. We have the framework and will be focusing on adding content.

Second, Large Language Models (LLMs) such as GPT 4, Bard, and Claude emerged in 2023 that could analyze and translate not only Latin (for which Google Translate had provided some initial, though flawed, machine translation) but also Ancient Greek – something that we had never expected to see. David Bamman collected c. 800 million words of digitized Latin in 2010. All surviving Ancient Greek literature probably amounts to less than 150 million words and only about 50 million words of Greek were available for training. Suddenly, we had multiple systems able not only to translate but to give grammatical explanations about each word and summarize and generate reading comprehension questions for passages in Ancient Greek. No one trained these LLMs to analyze Greek. They learned how to work with Greek and Latin by working with data in these and many other languages. Where machine learning had allowed us to build applications for specific functions such as morpho-syntactic parsers and automatic translation alignment systems, the LLMs were learning in a much more general way. For the first time, readers with no knowledge of Ancient Greek and Latin were able to use online systems to translate Greek and Latin sources and then to question each system about its decisions and compare their results against one another.

LLMs can not only generate high-performing translations but generate annotations such as the regularized dictionary form, glossing, and basic grammatical explanations, link named entities in context to their most likely Wikipedia pages, and associate pronouns with the entities to which they refer (coreference resolution). LLMs will allow us to generate many of the annotations that we present in Beyond Translation. The Beyond Translation framework may well become even more important more quickly than we had expected because so much new data may become available.

In general, our recommendations for other projects is always to be cautious in estimating what you can accomplish if you are doing something which you have not done multiple times before. We were lucky not to hit major unexpected roadblocks – that was, in fact, the most unexpected part of the project.

6. Project continuation and long-term impact

Beyond Translation represents the latest stage in the ongoing development of the Perseus Digital Library. We see no end to this development process and expect to build on Beyond Translation going forward. Our immediate goal is to replace the now venerable production version of Perseus, Perseus 4 (“[the Hopper](#)”) by fall 2024. To do so we will essentially add features from Beyond Translation to the Scaife Viewer.

We were fortunate to receive a Humanities Collections and Reference Resources grant ([PW-290565-23](#)) from the NEH for [Perseus on the Web – the Next Thirty Years](#). This grant will allow us to add the Beyond Translation services to the Scaife Viewer, a scalable system that we released in 2018 and that Brill has adopted for [its scholarly editions](#). This will allow us to

expand some of the core features in Perseus: we have already addressed the need to support critical editions. Additional work includes (1) treating uncorrected OCR-generated text and page images as a first class entity; (2) integrating metadata for all Greek and Latin sources through 600 CE, not just those for which we have TEI XML; (3) supporting text reuse detection (e.g., Plato quoting Homer).

Support from the [Tufts Data Intensive Studies Center](#), from the Tufts Arts and Science Administration, and from the Tufts Technology Services will also allow us to conduct crucial work needed to replace the current version of Perseus (Perseus 4.0: “the Hopper”) with a long-needed Perseus 5. This work includes support for accessibility, URL mapping, and a substantial amount of configuration so that the new Perseus can draw upon multiple CPUs to serve an audience that currently exceeds 300,000 unique users a month. Where Beyond Translation currently makes it possible to create a new form of digital edition, the Beyond Translation functionality will become a standard part of production Perseus.

We will continue to write grants to further research and development of various kinds. We do, however, see finally another path for sustaining the core services upon which digital libraries such as Perseus 5 will depend. Brill adopted the code base that Perseus and Eldarion developed for the Scaife Viewer. This code base now supports all of [Brill’s Digital Editions](#). The Brill content is proprietary. The Scaife Viewer code base, to which Brill contributes, is open. The result is that libraries, in paying subscriptions to Brill, are now making modest and indirect contributions to Perseus infrastructure. It may well be that libraries ultimately pay a commercial entity such as Brill to manage their open data infrastructure. MIT Press and the Media Lab created another structure, the [Knowledge Futures](#) non-profit, to charge subscriptions to libraries to manage infrastructure. An organization such as the New Alexandria Foundation, with closer ties to the study of the pre-modern world, provides another non-profit organization that could collect revenue and manage infrastructure

Areas for new research and development:

- Publishing ideas about Greek and other languages for a broader audience: We can now make visible to a wider audience aspects of primary sources that traditionally required knowledge of the language. We cannot yet, but we surely will soon, be able to embed the functionality available on Beyond Translation in other documents: e.g., a grammar or an article that includes not only Greek and English translations but also alignments between them, treebanking etc. In order to exploit this possibility, we will need to rethink how we write and test different approaches.
- Generalizing to other languages: The Universal Dependency Framework that we now use for Treebanks has been applied to more than 100 languages. LLMs can now provide much better support for other Classical languages such as Classical Persian, Classical Arabic, and pre-modern Japanese than was available before, making it much more feasible to add sources in languages such as these to Beyond Translation.

- AI vs. Machine Learning: As noted above, we are finally seeing systems that are going beyond using machine learning for specific tasks and learning much more generally (e.g., to perform a range of tasks for ancient Greek and Classical Persian). AI has been a buzz word for decades. We have (in PI Crane's view) encountered the biggest jump in forty years and we cannot assume that we know how this will end.
- The other AI — Augmented Intelligence: Beyond Translation is an application that augments human intelligence. Augmented Intelligence is, in fact, a research area in its own right with a dedicated [National Science Foundation funding program](#). We do know that readers can do things with a reading environment such as Beyond Translation that were impossible in print. But if we can see that something has changed and that new things are happening, we cannot precisely describe or measure those effects yet. Now that we have a functioning system, we can begin studying its effect.

Projects from which Beyond Translation imported data

1. The Cambridge Greek Lexicon: <https://www.classics.cam.ac.uk/research/projects/glp>.
2. The Daphne Treebank repository of Ancient Greek Poetry: <https://github.com/francescomambrini/Daphne>
3. Didakta Modular Greek Grammar: <https://github.com/farnoosh-shamsian/Didakta>.
4. The Digital Latin Library: <https://digitallatin.org/>,
5. The Homer Multitext Project: <https://www.homermultitext.org/>.
6. Hypotactic: <https://hypotactic.com/>.
7. Logeion: <https://logeion.uchicago.edu/Logeion>.
8. The New Alexandria Open Commentary Platform: <https://oc.newalexandria.info/>.
9. Open Greek and Latin: <https://www.opengreekandlatin.org/>.
10. The Pelagios Network: <https://pelagios.org/>.
11. Pedalion Treebanks: <https://www.relicta.org/pedalion/trees.php>.
12. The Perseids Project: <https://www.perseids.org/>.
13. The Pleiades gazetteer and graph of ancient places: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/>.
14. The Syntax Treebank Annotator: <https://github.com/gregorycrane/syntax-treebank-annotator>.
15. The Ugarit Alignment Platform: <https://ugarit.ialigner.com/>.

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